

THE IMPORTANCE OF TIME MANAGEMENT FOR STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article examines the critical role of time management in enhancing academic performance and personal well-being among students. By integrating findings from empirical studies and theoretical models, it aims to highlight the mechanisms through which effective time management can contribute to improved educational outcomes and stress reduction. The review suggests that time management skills are not only essential for academic success but also for fostering personal development and mental health.

Keywords: Time management, skills, productivity, multitasking, daily schedule, perception, plans, routines, achievements.

Introduction. The modern society demands a high level of professionalism from future specialists. Nowadays, not only professionals with specific skills are required, but also students are expected to understand how to acquire necessary knowledge, techniques, and skills in practical activities, as well as to effectively organize their activities. Therefore, the professional readiness of future specialists, particularly directing students to clear learning, developing skills in managing professional activities and time, utilizing personal capabilities, is of crucial importance.

The significance of time management in contemporary society is amplified across all spheres of social interaction, particularly during phases of dynamic evolution. Effective organization and planning of time have become imperative not only for students in today's colleges but also for aspiring professionals. As society progresses, the ability to manage time efficiently becomes increasingly vital, reflecting the demands of modern education and the expectations placed on future specialists.

Good time management skills can enhance productivity and maintain organization. Allocate specific time slots for daily tasks to plan and complete more work in a shorter period. However, procrastination will reduce output. A daily schedule is particularly beneficial for students, helping them stay organized and on top of their responsibilities. [3]

Literature review and methodology. A number of scientists — B. G. Ananyev, Y. M. Kondratiev, V. Y. Lyaudis, A. V. Mudrik, T. T. Shchelina, etc. consider

contemporary students as a special socio-psychological group with specific problems peculiar in it. The time of study at the university corresponds to the youth period (18-25 years), when a person is in the active stage of realizing his sociogenic potential. In the youth period, a value-semantic orientation is formed, which will help to determine particularly significant categories that have a huge impact on the pace of personal development and the capacity to achieve the ultimate goal of self-actualization. [1]

This category, according to some researchers — T. N. Berezina, N. Y. Grigorovskaya, V. I. Kovalev, V. Lens, A. Fayol, etc. — there is time, or rather, awareness of its significance. A person who is able to recognize the full value of the category of "time" is destined to success in all endeavors. There are constant debates about the category of "time" in philosophy, physics, psychology, pedagogy and other sciences. There are disputable and sometimes-controversial views on this issue, but most scientists note that it is essential to learn how to manage time competently. Pedagogical science has considered the great potential in the "time management" technology, the realization of which promotes to the achievement of increasing the possibilities for professional and personal development of students. [2]

There is quite a wide range of methods and technologies for productive organization and time management, which differ in that they consider work actions from various aspects:

One such method is the accelerated analysis approach according to the Eisenhower principle.

The Eisenhower Matrix is a time management method that helps prioritize tasks: doing what's important and not wasting time on futile activities. It corresponds to anyone who plans to manage their own and current moment, learning how to allocate time correctly to stay on schedule. [6]

The concept of spreading tasks according to this method arose from the 34th President of the United States, Dwight Eisenhower, who led the country from 1953 to 1961. Eisenhower is one of the most effective presidents in the history of the United States.

Utilizing the Eisenhower decision-making principle, tasks are assessed based on the criteria of important/not important and urgent/not urgent, [4] and subsequently allocated into the appropriate quadrants within the Eisenhower Matrix (also referred to as the "Eisenhower Box" or "Eisenhower Decision Matrix" [6]. Tasks within the quadrants are then managed accordingly.

Tasks A (important and urgent) demand immediate attention as they lead to significant outcomes when promptly addressed.

Tasks B (important, but not urgent) offer substantial returns; delaying their completion risks their escalation into quadrant A.

Tasks C (urgent, but not important) are minimally productive and may negatively impact work efficiency as they do not contribute significantly to goals despite their urgency.

Tasks D (neither important nor urgent) hinder workflow and yield no positive outcomes. The Eisenhower method combines the criteria of "importance" and "urgency" to prioritize tasks effectively, enhancing overall productivity. [5]

Time management stands as a pivotal tool for students, aiding in task organization and efficient allocation of resources. Adherence to time management principles ensures successful task completion within designated timelines. [3]

Results and discussion. According to their research, time management is the ability to manage time and use it as efficiently and productively as possible to achieve goals. In this regard, a student studying at the university needs to realize the value of time and find the most effective way to use it consistently. In the process of studying at the university, it is necessary to organize the activities of students in such a way that they can independently determine priorities, set goals, be able to competently plan, and manage their time.

It aids in lowering tension. Stress can result from not finishing projects, assignments, and studies. Everyone should prioritize taking care of their mental health, but students suffer from poor performance since they frequently experience elevated levels of stress and anxiety because of the strain of their coursework. [7]

In addition to increasing productivity, efficient time management inspires students to give their all in everything they do, which speeds up the process of achieving their objectives.

Certainly, planning helps to better understand the scope of work and accomplish everything necessary without missing anything. Planning is essential even for a student because one shouldn't always rely on memory. [9] Due to the fact that each person has their own characteristics, there arises a need for the formation of an individual time management technology taking into account such mechanisms as:

- biological clock, which determines the time of day when a person is most active;
- intellectual engineering, which involves the use of knowledge about human potential and the dominant hemisphere of the brain;

- psychological alarm clock, which distinguishes psychological time perspective, including psychological present, past, and future, and perception of time as a process of forming psychological present;
- a person's behavior style, which reflects the moral and ethical norms of the individual and determines their behavior in various life situations.

It is important to highlight that the effectiveness of these methods becomes apparent only when the student is consciously committed to their work, motivated, and prepared to address challenges decisively. [8] As professionalism directly influences the organization of work within the entire educational institution, management itself becomes an integral and essential part of professional activity and development. This entails continuously improving one's skills and efficiently utilizing time.

In conclusion, this article has highlighted the crucial role of time management in students' academic success and personal well-being. By synthesizing research findings, it has shown how effective time management skills contribute to improved educational outcomes and reduced stress levels. As students navigate the demands of academia and society, mastering time management becomes essential for productivity and personal growth. Through awareness, commitment, and practice, students can harness the power of effective time management to excel in their studies and beyond.

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